

Table 1. Foliage and grain yield from CN705-18. Chinsurah, India, 1988.

Parameter	Control (no cut)	1 cut	2 cuts
Foliage yield (t/ha)			
1st cut	—	3.8	3.6
2d cut	—	—	3.4
At harvest	2.1	1.9	2.0
Total	2.1	5.7	9.0
Grain yield (t/ha)	1.0	1.1	1.4
Days to 50% flowering	171	175	167

similar. Yields in the double cut crop were higher. Flowering was early in the double cut crop, followed by the normal crop and by the single cut crop.

Number of effective tillers at harvest was significantly higher in the double cut crop and 1,000-grain weight

Table 2. Effect of leaf cutting on yield components. Chinsurah, India.

Character	Treatment			Percent increase or decrease over control
	No cut	1 cut	2 cuts	
Plant ht (cm)	205.0	200.0	182.0	- 11
Effective tillers at harvest (no.)	6.0	10.0	12.0	+100
Panicle length (cm)	23.4	22.0	22.5	- 4
Total grains per panicle	202.0	185.0	156.0	- 23
1000-grain wt	24.1	24.3	25.4	+ 5
Percent of sterile grains/panicle	1.9	3.6	4.2	-
Yield per plant (gm)	28.0	41.0	45.0	+ 61
Grain-to-straw ratio	0.5	0.5	0.7	-

increased slightly. Grain yield/plant and grain-to-straw ratio also increased. Plant height, total grains/panicle, and length of panicle were reduced (Table 2).

The increased number of effective tillers contributed 61% of the yield increase. The shorter plant height

contributed to better grain filling.

This preliminary study shows that herbage production is possible with photoperiod-sensitive deepwater rice, without sacrificing grain yield. □

Improving rice yield using hydrocortisone spray

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The effect of hydrocortisone, a glucocorticoid hormone of higher animals, has been found to be beneficial for germination of rice. We assessed the effect of hydrocortisone on dry matter production, grain yield, and harvest index.

Hydrocortisone (50 ppm) was sprayed at different growth stages—active tillering phase (50 d after sowing [DAS]), flowering (75 DAS), and grain filling (100 DAS)—of a standing crop of IR20 at Karaikal. Spraying at flowering significantly improved grain yield and increased dry matter production (see table). Dry matter production increased most with spray at active tillering phase, but yield increased only 12%.

This trend suggests that dry matter production is stimulated by hydrocortisone spray during tillering phase, but its use for increasing grain productivity is limited. Similarly, spraying at grain filling phase did not

Effect of spraying hydrocortisone at different growth stages on yield, dry matter production, and harvest index per plot basis (16 m²).^a Pondicherry, India.

	Control	Active tillering (50 DAS)	Flowering (75 DAS)	Grain filling (100 DAS)	LSD (5%)
Yield (g)	9.10	10.21 (12)	11.00 (21)	10.30 (13)	1.16
Dry matter production (g)	21.81	26.38 (21)	25.58 (17)	24.70 (13)	4.04
Harvest index	0.41	0.39 (-6)	0.43 (4)	0.41 (-2)	ns

^aFigures in parentheses indicate percentage increase over control.

improve grain yield or dry matter production. To improve dry matter production and grain yield

simultaneously, a spray or hydrocortisone of 50 ppm at flowering stage is optimum. □

Soil fertility and fertilizer management

Using a chlorophyll meter to predict need for topdressed nitrogen

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Preliminary results show that a hand-held chlorophyll meter comes closer

than any other technique as a simple, quick, and accurate method for predicting the need to topdress N in semidwarf rice. A relationship between the chlorophyll content of the newest expanded leaf and the need for N fertilizer has been developed in 2 yr of experiments in research plots at Beaumont and in 1 yr at Bay City and Eagle Lake, Texas (see table).

We tested semidwarf Lemont variety

Relationship between leaf chlorophyll content and rice yield. Beaumont, Texas.

Chlorophyll reading	Expected yield increase (t/ha)	Expected net return to topdressing N (\$)
20	1.4	93
30	0.7	37
35	0.4	17
40	0.1	(-3)

topdressed with 45 kg/ha 2 wk before and at panicle differentiation. Net income due to topdressing decreased as leaf chlorophyll increased.

When chlorophyll readings were near 39 and higher, there was no economic advantage to topdressing N (assuming urea = \$165/t, application cost = \$8.64/ha, and rice value = \$8/cwt).

The chlorophyll meter (model SPAD-501 developed by Minolta) does have limitations: initial cost = \$1400. But fertilizing a 40-ha field with 45 kg N/ha also = approximately \$1400. Another limiting factor is that leaf chlorophyll can be influenced by P, Zn, and Fe deficiencies; low temperature; rice variety; growth stage; and herbicides. □

Economy in combining fertilizer N with green manure in lowland rice

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We studied the integrated effect of organic + inorganic N on rice yield and N use efficiency and recovery during wet season 1988. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. The soil is silt loam classed as Aquic Hapludoll, with pH 7.9, 1.1% organic C, CEC 20 meq/100 g, and 0.1% total N.

For green manure, 50-d-old crops of *Sesbania rostrata* and *S. aculeata* were chopped and incorporated into the top 15 cm soil at 10 and 20 t/ha, respectively, 1 wk before transplanting. Farmyard manure (FYM), 20 t/ha fresh weight basis, was incorporated 1 mo before transplanting. Pant Dhan 4 was sown 1 Jun and transplanted 11 Jul. All plots received 17.6 kg P, 24.2 kg K, 10 kg Zn/ha before transplanting. N was applied per treatment (see table).

Yield with *Sesbania* alone equaled yield with 90 kg N as prilled urea (PU). *Sesbania* with 30 kg N as PU increased the grain yield 9%, which was significantly higher than that with 90 kg N as PU alone and equaled yield with 120 kg N as PU or USG.

Highest N use efficiency and apparent N recovery was with *Sesbania* alone.

S. rostrata proved no better than *S. aculeata*, probably because it had only half the biomass. □

Effect of organic and inorganic N source on yield, N uptake, N use efficiency, and apparent N recovery in rice.^a Pantnagar, India, 1988.

Treatment	Time and rate of N			Grain yield (t/ha)	N uptake (kg/ha)			N use efficiency (kg grain/kg N applied)	Apparent N recovery (%)	
	Basal through	PU			Total N (kg/ha)	Grain	Straw			Total
		6-7	DBPI							
	GM	PU								
Control	0	0	0	0	3.8	54	24	78	-	
USG	0	80	40	120	5.8	95	61	156	17	
PU	0	80	40	120	5.7	93	46	139	16	
PU	0	50	40	90	5.4	82	51	133	18	
SA ^b + PU	60	20	40	120	6.1	101	55	155	19	
SR ^b + PU	40	40	40	120	6.1	100	55	155	19	
FYM ^b + PU	50	30	40	120	6.1	100	45	145	19	
SA + PU	60	30	0	90	6.0	100	44	144	24	
SR + PU	40	30	0	70	5.8	96	42	138	29	
FYM + PU	50	30	30	110	5.0	77	38	118	11	
SA	60	0	0	60	5.3	87	46	113	25	
SR	40	0	0	40	5.2	75	33	108	38	
LSD (0.05)					0.4	6	7	11	-	

^aGM = green manure, USG = urea supergranule (46% N), PU = prilled urea (46% N), SA = *Sesbania aculeata* (2% N, 80% moisture), SR = *Sesbania rostrata* (1.75% N, 83% moisture), FYM = farmyard manure (0.5% N, 50% moisture). ^bN content in sesbania and FYM was analyzed, The remaining N was applied through PU to meet the basal requirement of 80 kg N/ha. The rest or 1/3 of 120 kg N was applied at 6-7 d before panicle initiation (DBPI).

Effect of deep-placed urea supergranules (USG) with limited green manure on transplanted rice yield

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The amount of green manure available in small rainfed rice farmers' fields is likely to be very limited. In 1988 wet season, we compared the effect of deep-placed USG and split-applied prilled

urea (PU) alone and in combination with limited amounts of *Gliricidia sepium* leaves on rainfed transplanted rice.

The 11 treatments were laid out in 15-m² plots on the RARS farm, Karjat, in a randomized block design with three replications. Soil was clay loam with pH (1:2.5 soil:water) 7.0 and cation exchange capacity 30 meq/100 g. All plots received 17 kg P/ha as single superphosphate and 33 kg K/ha as potassium chloride.

PU (38 kg N/ha) was applied 50% broadcast and incorporated before transplanting and 50% topdressed before panicle initiation. USG (1-g pellets) was hand placed about 10 cm deep during